

Diversity and inclusion in mathematics teacher education: Lessons from Chile and Sweden

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Based on the examination of Chilean and Swedish research, the symposium addresses the possibilities and challenges for researching diversity and inclusion in mathematics pre- and in-service teacher education. Departing from concrete localized research and its contextual, theoretical and methodological stances, larger reflections and implications for the education of mathematics teachers that may lead to an increased sensitivity towards students' diversities and their impact in inclusion of students and change of educational experiences in mathematics are drawn.

Motivation

Transnational reports point to the correlation between students' diversities, including gender, socio-economic disadvantages, racial and ethnic differences, immigration background, etc., and low-performance in mathematics (e.g., OECD, 2014). The sharp inequities in results seem to undermine students' opportunities to access higher education and to break the poverty circle in which they live. Therefore, the connection between students' diverse position of disadvantage and the access to quality mathematics education is a problem to tackle by research in the field of mathematics education. This is an issue in many countries, among those Chile and Sweden, which have taken in substantial number of immigrants and have explicit policies for promoting equitable access to education.

The Chilean educational system is characterized by a deeply rooted inequity. Recent reform policies have taken steps towards improving quality and access to education. The "Law of inclusion" (MINEDUC, 2015) disallows schools to select students which is likely to

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help disadvantaged students; and the primary mathematics curriculum was re-written with a greater emphasis on problem solving (MINEDUC, 2012), as a way to improve the quality of education and students' results. However, little is known in about racial and ethnic minority students' mathematics experiences and performance, and about the challenges in educating teachers to implement reform-based mathematics instruction in diverse school contexts in Chile. Few studies have explored the teachers' learning process to teach mathematics to diverse student populations. This research sheds light on how teachers' views of students in positions of disadvantage play a critical role in successfully implementing reform-based mathematics instruction (Darragh & Valoyes-Chávez, 2019). Overall, the teacher is left to cope with other aspects of teaching, such as dealing with students' diversity.

In Sweden, educational policies have responded to the increase of diversity in student population by guaranteeing school attendance and thereby opening opportunities for social mobility and integration. The Swedish Agency of Education has launched reforms emphasizing students' attainment (Skolverket, 2015). Thus, success is equated to mathematics scores in a hierarchical system of evaluation. Even though gender differences in achievement have diminished, particular gender stereotypes are reproduced in mathematics teaching (Sumpter, 2016). Immigrant students' lower results in mathematics persists. Studies have focused on the impact of the language of instruction and students' home languages as a barrier or resources for learning mathematics (Caligari et al., 2021). The results show that teaching practices generate exclusion, and that teachers' views on students' abilities given their gender, socio-economic status or ethnicity are influential in students' opportunities for learning.

Furthermore, teacher education – initial and in-service – is recognized as a key for addressing diversity and generating inclusion of students in disadvantaged positions (Darling-Hammond, 2017). Researchers contend that a different type of understanding is needed to teach mathematics in diverse school settings (e.g., Anderson & Stillman, 2013). Thus, the question remains of how to educate teachers to support the mathematics learning of diverse student populations, so that quality and inclusion can go hand in hand; as well as of how research may support such education.

Aim

This symposium addresses the general problem of the challenges that students' diversity and its impact on more equitable school results pose for mathematics teacher education research. By taking the case of Chile and Sweden as a point of departure, the symposium aims at: (1) Discussing experiences that led to challenging teachers' education through distinctive research approaches to notions of inclusion and diversity. (2) Identifying theoretical and methodological ways of reasoning and operate with inclusion and diversity in mathematics teacher education research. (3) Rethinking the complexity of inclusion and diversity and its implications and possibilities for mathematics teacher education practices in different social contexts.

Organization

The symposium has a series of thematic conversations among researchers from Chile and Sweden. Each conversation involves a statement by each participant (10 m each), a time for discussion among them (5 m) and a time for conversation with the audience to draw connections with other contexts and problems (15 m). The symposium convener (Valero) will moderate the symposium. It is planned to take for 180 m.

Opening concerns: An introduction (10 m)

The symposium starts with a motivation by the convener for the topic and a series of questions about the relevance of the discussion for research and teacher education.

Challenging policies of inclusion and diversity (40 m)

This theme unfolds experiences that led to challenge inclusion and diversity in mathematics teacher education. The intention is to build an understanding of how diversity has entered the scene of mathematics teacher education practices and institutions in different settings. We draw on an experience with a group of embroiderers in Mexico to discuss how culture-centric views of mathematics can be questioned from cultural diversity perspectives to account for historically marginalized social groups' relationship to knowledge and school (Solares et al., forthcoming) Drawing on a teachers' experience in multilingual classrooms, we address the collision of expectations promoted—and imposed—by Swedish curricular guidelines, teacher training programs and parents (Caligari et al., 2021).

Dealing with teacher education's paradoxes (40 min)

This theme explores theoretical tools to trouble the current (and historical) state of mathematics teacher education. The toolboxes invite to examine the double gestures that make visible the paradoxes on mathematics teacher education. We explore how mathematics teacher education in Chile has been historically structured around discourses of a desired mathematics teacher in a constant state of becoming and quasi-Darwinism of mathematics teachers (Montecino, 2019). And, with this notion of the *image of a desired teacher* used for an analysis of policy and practice in teacher education, we show the operation of images as desire-constructs imposing inclusion/exclusion in teacher education in Sweden (Österling, 2021).

Experiences of diversity and inclusion in the mathematics classroom (40 min)

This theme focuses on how notions of diversity and inclusion are unfolded in particular research projects and educational settings. We revisit experiences collected in different school contexts and their implications for research. We discuss the limits of the Chilean law of inclusion and examine the challenges of implementing it in the case of Black immigrant students (Valoyes-Chávez & Darragh, under review). Then, we explore Swedish mathematics teacher's practices, based on research on multilingualism, to point call teacher educators for the need of elaborating different ways—both in practice and research—to cope with the diverse body of student teachers (Norén, 2015).

Challenges to and opportunities (40 min)

The symposium closes identifying key issues for further research and the implications for teacher education. We argue on how Chilean educational policies have been historically delineated to fabricate a particular citizen, currently attracted in making the global Homo-economicus that lead to invisibilize diversity and, therefore, negate inclusion (Andrade-Molina, in press). We also discuss whether inclusive methodologies that involve teacher students may be a path forward to generate new opportunities for inclusion for teacher students and teacher educators (Skog, 2014).

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